

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

INTRODUCTION OF AUTOMATION INTO THE QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN THE HEALTHCARE SECTOR OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

Kassenova G.,

*Participant in the 3rd group of the Global Leadership in Laboratory Activities program /
National Leadership in Laboratory Activities program in Kazakhstan
Almaty, Kazakhstan*

Beissegul A.,

*PhD, MBA, Doctoral Student DBA
Participant in the 3rd group of the Global Leadership in Laboratory Activities program /
National Leadership in Laboratory Activities program in Kazakhstan*

Kuatbayeva A.

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
Head of the Global Leadership in Laboratory Activities Program /
National Leadership Program in Laboratory Activities in Kazakhstan*

Abstract

The purpose of the study is to scientifically substantiate and design an information technology solution aimed at automating the quality management system (QMS) processes of medical laboratories in accordance with national and international requirements. Within the framework of this objective, it was assumed to identify the potential for the application of modern information technologies to support and optimize key QMS processes, as well as to assess the current state and prospects for the introduction of IT tools in the field of QMS automation in medical laboratories in the Republic of Kazakhstan. This work shows the extent to which the quality management system in the healthcare sector of Kazakhstan is currently ready for process automation. As part of this article, a survey was conducted among respondents, including administrative and management staff in the healthcare sector. This survey revealed the percentage of participants who use QMS in their organization, the methods of using QMS, and also helped to compare the use of the traditional (manual) method of QMS implementation and the automated approach. Analysis of the survey helped to identify the main advantages and barriers to the introduction of automation into the QMS in the healthcare sector. This issue remains relevant today for the Ministry of Health as a key tool in the management system of healthcare organizations.

Keywords: Automation, quality management system, QMS in healthcare, automation in healthcare.

Introduction

Recent studies emphasize that the introduction of digital quality monitoring tools can significantly reduce the number of laboratory errors and increase the clinical significance of results. For example, according to Plebani, the systematic use of quality indicators contributes to a reduction in errors at the pre-analytical stage by more than 30% [1, p.752]. Sciacovelli et al. point out that real-time visualization and analysis of KPIs create the basis for predictive risk management and process optimization [2, p.311].

The current stage of healthcare development is characterized by accelerated digital transformation aimed at improving the efficiency, transparency, and manageability of laboratory processes. As medical laboratories in the Republic of Kazakhstan transition to working in accordance with the requirements of the international standard ISO 15189:2023, as well as national regulatory documents, the formation of an effective quality management system (QMS) based on the principles of reproducibility, process traceability, and continuous improvement is becoming particularly important.

At the same time, preliminary research and practical analysis show that most Kazakhstani laboratories operate with a low degree of QMS automation: paper-

based or semi-automated forms of documentation prevail, which leads to an increase in the labor intensity of processes, an increased risk of errors, delays in updating the regulatory framework, and limited analytical capabilities. The conditions of high regulatory burden, staff shortages, and increasing requirements for the quality of laboratory services require the search for innovative tools that ensure sustainable and effective QMS management.

Under these conditions, the design of specialized software products intended for the automation of laboratory quality management system processes and taking into account the national realities of the Republic of Kazakhstan becomes a relevant scientific and applied task. A comprehensive study of the development and implementation of information technologies in the QMS of laboratories will not only ensure compliance with international requirements, but also increase the competitiveness of domestic laboratories, reduce operating costs, and improve the accuracy and speed of management decisions, which determines the significance and timeliness of the chosen research topic.

The quality management system (QMS) is a fundamental component that ensures the reliability, accuracy, and traceability of laboratory test results,

servicing as a tool for guaranteeing trust in the activities of medical laboratories. The implementation in the Republic of Kazakhstan of the international requirements of the ST RK ISO 15189–2023 standard, aimed at risk-based management and continuous improvement, necessitates the formalization and systematization of all QMS processes.

In today's environment, such activities are virtually impossible without the support of information and digital solutions that automate documentation, analysis, auditing, and corrective actions. However, despite the active spread of laboratory information systems (LIS) and other IT tools, the level of QMS automation in medical laboratories in Kazakhstan remains insufficient, and key processes are still carried out in a semi-automated or paper-based format.

International practice demonstrates the high effectiveness of implementing specialized software products for QMS management, which increase efficiency, reduce operating costs, and ensure compliance with accreditation requirements. This underscores the need to develop domestic information solutions tailored to the specifics of Kazakhstani laboratories, the national regulatory framework, and management needs.

Thus, the automation of the quality management system through the design of specialized software products is a relevant area of scientific research with significant potential for increasing the competitiveness of Kazakhstan's laboratory services, ensuring their sustainable development, and integrating them into the global laboratory medicine space.

Literature review

Modern quality management in healthcare laboratories is undergoing rapid transformation under the influence of digital transformation. One of the leading trends is the introduction of electronic quality management systems (eQMS), which automate key processes, including document management, CAPA procedures, internal audits, change management, training, and risk control [3, p. 252]. These systems provide centralized accounting and increased transparency in quality management.

A comprehensive example is the integration of eQMS with corporate systems: ERP, MES, CRM, and LIS, which enhances data management and improves the alignment of quality processes with manufacturing and laboratory operations [4, p. 156]. This approach provides end-to-end management—from sample registration to results.

Additional emphasis is placed on the use of artificial intelligence (AI) to improve the effectiveness of QMS. AI helps automate audits, identify deviations, predict risks, and support data-driven decision-making [5]. In particular, AI applications for visual quality inspection and explainable AI are showing growth in manufacturing systems [6].

The role of cloud-based solutions (SaaS-eQMS) is also growing. Thanks to their scalability and reduced infrastructure costs, these solutions are becoming popular among medical and pharmaceutical organizations [2, p. 324]. These solutions simplify access and quality management, especially in distributed laboratory networks.

Finally, international experience points to the need

for a change in organizational culture: digitalization of QMS requires IT skills, staff training, and change management, not just technical integration [4].

In the context of rapid digitalization and increasingly stringent regulatory requirements (e.g., ISO 15189, GMP, FDA, GxP), the transition from traditional paper forms to electronic quality management systems (eQMS) is becoming a critical step for most medical laboratories.

International experience in implementing electronic quality management systems (eQMS) in medical laboratories demonstrates a number of consistent trends that highlight both the relevance of these solutions and the risks associated with them. However, from a scientific and practical point of view, the key advantage of eQMS is the improvement of process efficiency and transparency through the centralization of documentation management, non-conformities, CAPA, audits, staff training, and risks. Electronic systems minimize the influence of the human factor, ensure consistency of procedures, version control, and compliance with deadlines, which is especially important in the context of increasingly stringent international standards.

International experience. Advantages of implementing a QMS

Increased process efficiency and transparency. eQMS automates key QMS functions—including document management, CAPA, auditing, risk control, and training—through digital workflows, reducing human error, and speeding up approvals [8].

Predictive analytics and artificial intelligence - Integrating AI/ML into eQMS enables failure prediction, anomaly detection, and risk-based decision-making, making the system more proactive compared to reactive models [7].

Cloud solutions and scalability - SaaS eQMS models simplify deployment, provide access across distributed laboratories, and reduce infrastructure and support costs, which is particularly important for fast-growing or resource-constrained institutions [3, p. 318].

Reduced compliance risks - Digitization of processes improves audit readiness, ensures traceability and version control, minimizing the risks of non-compliance with regulatory standards [3, p.319].

International experience. Risks and limitations

Technical and infrastructure dependence. Implementing eQMS requires a stable IT infrastructure, including reliable network connectivity, backup systems, and support—which can be challenging for regional laboratories with limited capabilities [3, p.320].

Resistance to change and staff training. Staff may experience difficulties transitioning to a new system, especially if there is a weak digital culture. The need for training and changes to organizational processes becomes a significant barrier to implementation [1, p. 753].

Increasing regulatory requirements. Modernization of standards (e.g., ISO updates or regulatory requirements) may require rapid adaptation of the eQMS, making the solution less stable without adequate support and vendor assistance [3, p.320].

Ethical and operational risks of AI. AI tools can generate algorithmic bias, transparency issues (black box), data security threats, and difficulties in explaining decisions—especially when such systems are not adequately monitored and audited [8].

Methodology

In the course of research on the topic “Information technologies in the quality management system of medical laboratories in the Republic of Kazakhstan: review, analysis, and design of software products,” it is advisable to use a set of complementary methods that ensure a comprehensive scientific study of the tasks set.

Theoretical and content analysis — to study the current state of the scientific and methodological base and global experience in the application of information technologies for the automation of quality management systems (QMS), as well as to analyze regulatory and legal documents (including Standard of Republic of Kazakhstan ISO 15189-2023, ISO 9001).

Online surveys and questionnaires (based on the Google Forms online platform) were used as empirical research methods to identify the actual level of automation of the quality management system, as well as barriers, needs, and expectations of key stakeholders (laboratory managers, quality specialists, IT personnel). The survey received responses from 127 QMS managers and laboratory specialists from various regions of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which provided representative data for subsequent analysis.

Statistical data processing methods — for processing survey results (descriptive statistics).

Comparative analysis and benchmarking methods — to compare domestic conditions with international eQMS practices and identify the best feasible solutions

Results and discussion

In the context of healthcare digitization, feedback from specialists directly involved in quality assurance processes is a critically important source of data for justifying design decisions.

To this end, a targeted survey was conducted among QMS managers and medical laboratory specialists in the Republic of Kazakhstan. This methodological step provided a representative picture of which functionalities of the electronic quality management system (eQMS) are most in demand, what barriers and limitations practitioners see, and what effects they expect from the introduction of digital tools.

The survey was organized in electronic format using the Google Forms platform and was conducted between April 25 and July 25, 2025. To ensure the reliability and transparency of the data obtained, the questionnaire was anonymous, which minimized the risk of response bias and increased the level of candor among respondents.

The target audience included quality managers and heads of medical laboratories in the Republic of Kazakhstan, who are direct stakeholders in the implementation of electronic solutions in the field of QMS. The study yielded 127 valid responses, which provides sufficient representativeness for analyzing the current state, barriers, and expectations in the context of the digitalization of laboratory management.

The results of the survey demonstrate a high level of implementation of the quality management system (QMS) in medical laboratories in the Republic of Kazakhstan. When asked, “Does your laboratory use a quality management system?” 92.1% of respondents (117 people) answered affirmatively, 5.5% (7 people) indicated partial use, while only 2.4% (3 people) reported the absence of a QMS (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – The proportion of quality management systems (QMS) used in medical laboratories

These data indicate that the vast majority of laboratories have already integrated quality management processes into their activities, reflecting the high level of relevance of this area and confirming the industry's focus on global trends related to the implementation of international quality standards. Thus, more than 90% of laboratories can be considered potential users of digital solutions for QMS.

At the same time, analysis of QMS implementation formats revealed significant variability in practices. Thus, the survey data presented in Figure 2 show that 57.5% of respondents continue to use paper-based QMS, which indicates a limited level of automation and high transaction costs in document management. Another 33.8% of respondents use general-purpose electronic tools (Microsoft Word and Excel) for documentation management, which reflects an intermediate

stage of digitalization but does not provide comprehensive process automation. Only 8.7% of survey participants (respondents) reported using specialized software solutions that partially meet the needs of QMS management.

The identified imbalance between the formal implementation of QMS and the low level of digital maturity of its implementation tools indicates significant potential for the development and implementation of specialized eQMS software. These results confirm the need to move from fragmented and paper-based forms to comprehensive digital systems capable of improving efficiency, transparency, and compliance with international standards.

The results of a survey on difficulties in the functioning of quality management systems (QMS) in medical laboratories in the Republic of Kazakhstan reveal a complex set of systemic problems that hinder the improvement of process efficiency and compliance with international standards.

The most significant factor identified by 81.9% of respondents (104 people) was the large volume of paper documentation. This indicator suggests that the majority of QMSs operate within a traditional, document-centric paradigm (Table 1). This leads to excessive transaction costs, slower information updates, and significant limitations for analytics. In the context of global digitalization, this model demonstrates low sustainability, making the transition to eQMS an objective necessity.

Figure 2 – The proportion of traditional and digital forms of QMS documentation used in medical laboratories

Table 1

Main difficulties in the functioning of QMS in medical laboratories

Difficulties in the functioning of the QMS	Number of respondents	Share
Large volume of paper documentation	104	81,9%
Difficulty in tracking corrective actions	35	27,6%
Insufficient transparency of processes	30	23,6%
Challenges in preparing for internal/external audits	46	36,2%
Insufficient staff qualifications	33	26%

Table 1 also shows that 36.2% of participants (46 people) noted difficulties in preparing for internal and external audits. This indicates that existing systems do not provide the necessary level of automation for report generation and data archiving. As a result, the risk of non-compliance during inspections increases, which negatively affects the reputation of laboratories and complicates accreditation in accordance with the ST RK ISO 15189-2023 standard. The problem of the complexity of tracking corrective actions (CAPA) was highlighted by 27.6% of respondents (35 people). The lack of digital monitoring tools means that corrective and preventive actions often remain unsystematic and fragmented. As a result, process control is lost, and continuous improvement mechanisms, which are key to the ISO approach, are only partially implemented. 26% of respondents (33 people) pointed to insufficient staff qualifications. This factor is twofold: on the one hand,

it reflects a lack of digital technology skills, and on the other, it reinforces resistance to change. Thus, the implementation of eQMS should be accompanied by educational initiatives and the development of user interfaces that reduce the barriers to digital learning.

Finally, 23.6% of respondents (30 people) identified the problem of insufficient transparency of processes. This confirms the lack of a unified digital quality management framework and limited opportunities for analytical assessment of key performance indicators (KPIs). In the long term, this situation reduces the competitiveness of the laboratory industry at the regional and international levels.

The survey results revealed a set of barriers, presented in Table 2, that hinder the implementation and effective functioning of a quality management system (QMS) in medical laboratories in Kazakhstan.

Barriers to the implementation and operation of a quality management system (QMS)

Barrier	Number of respondents	%	Analytical commentary
Lack of resources (time, personnel, equipment)	85	66,9%	Structural deficiencies in organizational and material capabilities; staff overload and equipment shortages hinder eQMS integration without systematic support.
Lack of motivation among employees	47	37%	Reflects a weak quality culture and a formal perception of QMS; measures are needed to engage staff and develop a quality culture.
Difficulty in understanding standards	41	32,3%	Problems with interpreting international and national requirements (ISO 15189:2023); indicates the need for educational programs and digital assistants within eQMS.
Lack of software tools	46	36,2%	Confirms the predominance of manual processes; limits analytics and monitoring capabilities, which reduces the effectiveness of quality management.
Lack of support from management	21	16,5%	Indicates systemic risk of low priority for QMS without management involvement; institutionalization of quality processes is necessary.

The most critical factor was identified as a lack of resources (66.9%), including staff shortages, time constraints, and a lack of equipment. This result demonstrates that even with the high regulatory significance of QMS, its practical implementation is complicated by institutional and organizational constraints. In conditions of staff shortages, the introduction of digital solutions is perceived as an additional burden rather than a means of optimization, which reduces the likelihood of successful eQMS integration without parallel resource support from the state and organizational management.

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A significant proportion of respondents noted the difficulty in understanding standards (32.3%), which indicates a gap between the regulatory framework (e.g., ISO 15189:2023) and the practical skills of staff. This

confirms the relevance of educational initiatives aimed at interpreting and adapting standards to the national context. In turn, insufficient support from management (16.5%), although less significant, reflects a key risk: without strategic leadership and institutionalization of processes, quality remains on the periphery of management priorities.

Table 3 presents data showing that respondents' expectations from the implementation of an electronic quality management system (QMS) program are predominantly pragmatic in nature and focused on solving the most pressing operational problems. The largest number of participants (81.1%) associate the digitization of QMS with the possibility of significant time savings. This result reflects laboratories' fatigue with paper-based processes and their receptiveness to automation as a tool for increasing productivity and reducing routine costs.

The second most important factor (60.6%) is reducing the number of errors, which confirms the need for laboratories to have digital verification mechanisms, automatic reminders, and standardized work scenarios. This indicates a desire to move from reactive error correction to error prevention, which is consistent with the principles of ISO 15189:2023, where the key emphasis is on preventing non-conformities.

Analysis of expected benefits from the implementation of the electronic QMS program

Advantage	Percentage of respondents	Number of respondents	Analytical interpretation
Time savings	81,1%	103	The most significant expected effect. Emphasizes the high time costs of paper-based document flow and manual processes. QMS automation is seen as the key to improving operational efficiency and reducing labor costs.
Reduction in the number of errors	60,6%	77	The second most important advantage. Points to the problems of manual data entry, duplication, and insufficient standardization. Confirms the need for built-in control mechanisms and automatic notifications in eQMS.
Simplifying audit preparation	53,5%	68	Reflects the value of digitization for compliance with ISO 15189:2023 and national standards. The electronic system facilitates documentation structuring, reporting automation, and CAPA transparency, which is critical for audits.
Increasing process transparency	51,2%	65	Expectations for the elimination of “information gaps” and the formation of a unified digital quality management system. Laboratories are striving to transition from fragmented document management to centralized systems.
Improving customer service quality	46,5%	59	Almost half of respondents associate eQMS with increased customer satisfaction. This confirms the understanding of the relationship between internal quality process efficiency and laboratory market competitiveness.

Expectations related to facilitating audit preparation (53.5%) reflect the high level of regulatory pressure on laboratories. Here, eQMS is seen as a tool for systematizing documentation, maintaining digital logs, and transparently tracking corrective actions (CAPA). This reduces the risk of non-compliance and simplifies interaction with external auditors.

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Finally, improving customer service (46.5%) demonstrates an understanding of the relationship between internal efficiency and market competitiveness. Laboratories associate digital transformation not only with the optimization of internal processes, but also with increased trust from patients and customers.

The high percentage of respondents (77.2%) who expressed interest in implementing an electronic QMS program indicates that medical laboratories have a clear demand for the digitization of quality processes. This result demonstrates not only a readiness to implement new technologies, but also an awareness of the strategic importance of eQMS as a tool for optimizing document flow, reducing operating costs, and ensuring compliance with international standards, including ISO 15189:2023. Thus, there is a solid foundation for the widespread adoption of digital solutions in the field of laboratory management.

However, 18.1% of respondents represent the segment of laboratories that are in a state of “digital anticipation.” Despite their potential interest, they are cautious due to a lack of clear understanding of the necessary resources, implementation costs, and expected

effectiveness. This most likely reflects either a lack of financial resources or insufficient digital literacy among employees. For this segment, the key factor in promoting eQMS will be demonstrating successful practical cases, pilot projects, and educational initiatives that reduce uncertainty and increase confidence in the results of digitalization.

Conclusion

Thus, the results of the study demonstrate that the key obstacle to the effective functioning of the quality management system in medical laboratories in Kazakhstan remains its document-centric nature, which places an excessive burden on staff and hinders the efficiency of processes. This factor is the main determinant of the transition to digital solutions. Automating the processes of preparing for audits and tracking corrective actions (CAPA) appears to be a priority task that can ensure compliance with the requirements of ISO 15189:2023 and reduce the likelihood of critical non-conformities. The human factor, manifested in insufficient staff qualifications, highlights the need for systematic programs to improve digital literacy and introduce ergonomic eQMS interfaces that minimize the risk of user errors. Insufficient process transparency further confirms the need to create a unified digital platform that provides data integration, end-to-end control, and analytical support for decision-making. Taken together, the identified factors indicate that the transition to an electronic quality management system (eQMS) in Kazakhstan's laboratory industry cannot be considered an optional step, but is a strategically necessary condition for strengthening competitiveness, sustainability, and compliance with global trends in the digital transformation of healthcare.

A comprehensive analysis reveals the need for an integrated approach to QMS digitalization, including:

- resource provision (funding, equipment, personnel),
- the formation of a culture of quality through motivational mechanisms,
- the introduction of specialized eQMS as a technological foundation,
- educational programs to improve digital and regulatory literacy,
- involvement of managers to reinforce the priority of QMS at the institutional level.

The comprehensive analysis confirms that the electronic QMS program is perceived by respondents as a strategic tool capable of solving three key tasks:

- Operational efficiency — through time savings and error reduction.
- Regulatory resilience — through simplified audit preparation and ensuring compliance with international standards.

Thus, the transition to eQMS goes beyond technical modernization and takes on strategic importance: it ensures the transition of Kazakhstan's laboratories from fragmented management to a proactive, integrated quality model in line with global trends in the digital transformation of healthcare.

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